

PRINCIPLES AS WELL AS TECHNIQUES FOR MATERIALS DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: Specifying language teaching and learning content is a crucial first step in generating resources for a language program. Content specification involves preparing a list of elements to be taught in a specified order, taking into account aspects such as the course setting, learners' requirements, and teaching principles (Nation & Macalister, 2010). Content definition optimizes interactions between input, learner, and learning process. Kumaravadivelu (2006) suggests that after determining the input, curriculum development should focus on the content and design of classroom activities and resources. Local materials production progresses throughout time, reflecting historical shifts in language development and foreign language instruction. These changes also reflect developments in the economic, political, scientific, ideological, and technological realms, both locally and internationally. English language teaching resources date back to the Middle Ages, when contemporary vernacular languages were first taught. In 1396, the first French teaching textbook in England featured a list of popular talks for visitors to France. It followed the Latin tradition of teaching spoken Latin through dialogues or colloquies in a question-and-answer format, comparable to the catechistic technique of breaking down the subject into small chunks for memorization. Such debates sparked modern textbook debates. According to Canniveng and Martinez (2003), teachers' prior experiences and cognitions are frequently disregarded while developing training materials. INSETT courses generally push teachers to consider materials design philosophy before completing a simple project. According to Tomlinson (2003, p. 448), the actual benefits of material progress come from regulated experience rather than increasing knowledge from study. For trainee instructors, the most important aspect of materials design is reflection following design and usage, as well as the design process itself. EFL teacher training manuals sometimes disregard content development in favor of technique and English grammatical proficiency. McDonough, Shaw, and Masuhara (2013) are unique in that they focus on teacher assessment, adaptation, development, and material utilization.

Key words: INSETT, cross-cultural, ideological, vernacular languages, EFL, EAL textbooks, a polycentric strategy, local English varieties.

Introduction

Before delving into materials development difficulties, it's important to understand their origins and context. Materials don't exist in a vacuum. Stakeholders' philosophical and belief systems contribute to the overall context of language learning. Language resources vary based on their intended purpose and learning style. Materials cannot be separated from broader language and learning concerns. Materials are only one aspect of the learning process. Other factors include teachers, learners, sponsors, publishers, curriculum and syllabus, assessment system, material and economic conditions, and culture. When designing materials, we face a complex and frequently competing collection of criteria. As with so many things, it is not as straightforward as it appears. In teaching, it is important to consider the purpose of the resources used. Coursebooks are seen to be a valuable resource for both teachers and

students. This viewpoint suggests that they serve as a beneficial reference for users. Without them, the language would be disorganized and difficult to understand, with pieces of phonology, syntax, and meaning. They provide a graded sequence of linguistic and factual information, as well as chances for language practice and application, to promote effective language learning. Materials are supposed to provide larger educational views, including critical thinking, life skills, citizenship, global challenges, and cross-cultural understanding.

However, such items have drawn severe criticism. Although some professors may prefer otherwise, all courses are diverse. Each learner has unique characteristics such as aptitude, maturity, language development stage, motivation, personal experience, and more. Individual learners advance at their own pace and have diverse interests. According to Brown (2013), Prabhu (1998), and Underhill & Maley (2012), students' learning experiences are often unexpected. Course-book materials produced with a one-size-fits-all approach have been criticized for being inappropriate and irrelevant (Allright, 1981; Tomlinson & Masuhara, 2013). Some propose using resource materials (Maley, 1998; Prabhu, 1989) instead of course materials. Others propose teacher- or student-created resources as a solution. Proponents of Dogme (Meddings & Thornbury 2002) argue that published materials are unnecessary. Instead, they advocate for a 'learning conversation' that adapts to the dynamic between teacher and students at any given time. Underhill (Maley & Underhill, 2013; Underhill) expanded on the concept of continuous improvisation in response to changing circumstances.

Modifications throughout Time in Local Material Development

Local materials development develops with time, reflecting historical changes in language development and foreign language teaching. These changes also reflect changes in economic, political, scientific, ideological, and technical domains, both locally and globally. English language teaching materials originated with the teaching of modern vernacular languages throughout the Middle Ages. In 1396, the earliest French instruction textbook in England included a collection of common conversations for travelers visiting France. It maintained the Latin tradition of teaching spoken Latin via dialogues or colloquies in a question-and-answer style, similar to the catechistic practice of breaking up the material into manageable bits for memorizing. Such discussions gave rise to contemporary textbook discussions.

The first textbooks for teaching English to traders and immigrants from France were double-manual. The first was created by William Caxton (ca. 1422-ca. 91) and produced on his printing press. Unlike previous guides, this one is multilingual and practical, with easy sections that explain ordinary words. It also offers brief pictures of trade workers:

Martin Le especier	Martin the grocer
Vent plusieurs especes	Selleth many spyces
De toutes manieres de pouldre	Of all manner of poudre
Pour faire les brouets	For to make browettys (broths), etc.

(Howatt, 2004, p. 13)

Double-manuals published throughout Europe demonstrated the increasing necessity of speaking English. Gabriel Meurier, a Frenchman, was the first EFL instructor with a name. His double-manual, *A Treatise for to Learn to Speak French and English* (1553), aimed to educate

merchants how to write letters, indentures, and other trade-related documents. The second wave of Protestant refugees from France, Italy, and Spain led to the teaching of English as a foreign language in London, with bilingual refugee instructors who were natural speakers of their respective languages. The most notable one was Jacque Bellot, an EFL instructor. He produced guides for French-speaking migrants to improve basic reading skills.

The materials utilized throughout the seven-year graded teaching objectives were largely identical, but they were also tailored to the local language context. Where a colony already had a written language, such as French, both were taught. Local vernacular languages were excluded from these requirements. In such places, kids who attended local mission schools in their own language had to pupils must acquire spelling, grammar, and vocabulary, similar to EAL pupils, before enrolling in government schools that follow English standards. The materials used in these categories included reading passages from English standard writers, writing reports of things and occurrences, and repeating stories. The syllable reading method, popular in Britain during that period, was also used throughout the colonies. India, or the Second British Empire, is a distinct geopolitical example. The British presence in India resulted in the migration of administrators and the implementation of British school curriculum to train future leaders and governors (Howatt, 2004).

Over 375 million people worldwide use English as a first language, extending beyond Kachru's (1985) inner circle of English-speaking countries. Fifty additional nations identify as English-speaking, with English as their official or major language. In certain nations, such as the Netherlands, 80% of the population speaks English as their primary language for communication with the rest of the world, despite it not being an official language. The global growth of EAL has led to a diverse selection of resources tailored to local educational situations. Teachers utilize the Internet and multimedia to enhance instructional content with cultural and linguistic authenticity, both locally and worldwide. EAL textbooks written by Anglophone writers and published by Western publishers are available for worldwide consumption. They are often employed in areas with limited local resources. Several textbook series are customized for usage in distinct nations.

Materials Development's Future Direction

The future of English materials design is as complicated as the distinctions between first/second, native/foreign, international/global, lingua franca, and extra language. English's future purpose, use, and education cannot be fully understood based on its geographical spread alone. Examining English materials design in terms of global vs. local content, rather than localization, may provide a more accurate prediction of its future.

Globalization is widely recognized as a major sociopolitical and economic event. Instead of promoting one-way exports of products and technology, it appears to foster hybrid forms of culture, language, and political structure, defined by a dynamic of flow and counter-flow. For example, English influences other languages, which acquire English terms and phrases.

However, by doing so, English assumes certain communication functions. However, Cook and Singleton (2014) found that local languages can create hybrid forms of English. The nature and intensity of such flow varies.

Professionals and adult users require tailored resources that address their specific demands, including vocabulary, grammar, discourse, and pragmatics. That need is expected to grow momentum in the future. Increased interest in translating necessitates enhanced English

skills. Professional translators and interpreters remain in high demand in a multilingual environment, notwithstanding promises of machine translation and increased English education (European Commission, 2013; Kerr, 2014). Translation by machine is based on a data system that uses text corpora and dictionaries.

Humans use statistical methods to fine-tune a system that automatically generates translations. However, these translations still require human verification. Thus, the European Commission employs 2,500 professional translators in 25 European languages to do simultaneous, written, and web translations. Between 1997 and 2013, English translations increased from 45% (1.1 million pages) to 81% (2.02 million pages) of those authored in French and German (European Commission, 2013). Translation, like education, is becoming more professionalized. Translation is being used in English classrooms as both an end goal and a technique for promoting multilingualism. (Kerr, 2014). Meeting the requirements of young adults, particularly in Asia, is crucial for the future of English education and materials development. Electronic media is shaping global style as "hanging out" on the internet becomes the norm. To cater to the chosen themes and learning styles of young people, English language resources should include casual registers. Classrooms are increasingly using gaming tactics, mobile devices, and hybrid, mixed, and flipped learning models. Distance education has the potential to become a sustainable method of language teaching, not just as a supplement to traditional classroom settings.

Globally printed materials may be superseded by mobile applications developed by instructors or adapted from other fields. As technology advances, multimedia tools for online education will expand. According to Ellis (2014), notarized variants of English already contain identity markers for young learners, prompting publishers to use a polycentric strategy and produce resources in local English varieties.

Material design and teacher training

Historically, early teacher preparation courses did not prioritize materials production, possibly due to the assumption that teachers had the requisite knowledge or skills to build their own materials (Tomlinson 2003). Recently, there has been a shift in focus from 'knowledge about teaching and related topics' (Mann, 2005, p. 106) to a view of teacher education as an ongoing engagement between received and experiential knowledge. Mann believes that knowledge of materials is an important part of this new focus. Many undergraduate and master's level programs urge student-teachers to generate materials. However, it is unclear how instructors are prepared for this work and how materials are evaluated after teaching practice.

According to Canniveng and Martinez (2003), instructors' past experiences and cognitions are often overlooked while designing teaching materials. INSETT courses typically encourage teachers to think on materials design philosophy before practicing a basic assignment. According to Tomlinson (2003, p. 448), the true advantages of material development are achieved through regulated experience rather than increased knowledge from research. For trainee teachers, the most significant component of materials design is reflection after design and use, as well as the design process itself. EFL teacher training guides often overlook content development, instead emphasizing technique and English grammatical competence. McDonough, Shaw, and Masuhara (2013) focus on teacher assessment, adaptability, development, and material usage, making them an outlier. Books that provide advice on

materials development typically focus on mechanical elements of design, such as layout and visual appeal, to augment areas where practice is lacking in course books. The Borneo project aimed to help student-teachers comprehend the demands of different work kinds while also showcasing the aesthetics of successful materials creation. According to Johnson (2008), effective presentation of new language requires clarity and memorability. He highlights the need of teaching new linguistic points with clarity and memorability to ensure learners retain them. Innovative design and material selection may create memorable experiences.

Conclusion

Coursebooks are seen to be an invaluable resource for both teachers and students. This viewpoint implies that they act as a useful reference for users. Without them, the language would be chaotic and difficult to grasp, containing fragments of phonology, syntax, and meaning. They offer a graded sequence of linguistic and factual information, as well as opportunities for language practice and application, to encourage successful language acquisition. Materials are intended to promote broad educational perspectives, such as critical thinking, life skills, citizenship, global concerns, and cross-cultural understanding. The resources used for the seven-year graded teaching objectives were generally the same, but they were additionally customized to the local linguistic environment. In colonies that already had a written language, such as French, both were taught. Local vernacular languages were exempt from these criteria. In such regions, children who attended local mission schools in their native language had to learn spelling, grammar, and vocabulary, just like EAL students, before enrolling in government schools that followed English standards. These categories' resources included reading passages from English standard writers, making reports on items and happenings, and retelling stories. The syllable reading method, which was popular in Britain at the time, spread to the colonies as well. Specialists and people of all ages demand materials that are adapted to their individual needs, including vocabulary, grammar, discourse, and pragmatics. That demand is projected to gain traction in the future. Increased interest in translation needs improved English proficiency. Professional translators and interpreters remain in great demand in a multilingual world, despite promises of machine translation and improved English education (European Commission, 2013; Kerr, 2014). Machine translation is a data-driven system that works with text corpora and dictionaries.

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